

IMPORTANT TYPES OF EDUCATION AND METHODOLOGICAL RECOMMENDATIONS IN BIOETHICS

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ABSTRACT

The primary objective of studying bioethics in educational institutions is to provide students with knowledge about technical and technological objects and processes, teach them practical work methods, and develop personal qualities, creative thinking, and the ability to work independently.

Keywords: Education and the learning process.

In psychology, activity is regarded as a form of purposeful, conscious attitude and actions carried out by an individual. Any human activity, including learning and cognitive (mental) activity, does not yield the desired results without psychological preparation. Therefore, in the process of teaching specialized subjects, it is necessary to create conditions that awaken interest, enthusiasm, and desire in the learner towards the studied educational material, as well as to provide opportunities for logical and creative thinking.

Active cognition, as A.M. Matyushkin points out, emerges as a result of systematically presenting tasks one after another and creating problem situations. Since activity arises from consciousness, it also necessitates the coordination of content, forms, methods, and means of studying specialized disciplines. When determining the level of activity, the practical importance and degree of complexity of the material should be taken into account.

The third level of activity requires actions of a creative nature. It demonstrates creative activity aimed at achieving the intended learning goal. Partially exploratory activity takes on a fully creative character. The knowledge acquired at this level of activity is systematic, deep, and thorough, and can be utilized in any desired situation.

Thus, activity is considered an important aspect of student performance. The level of activity is determined, firstly, by the degree to which students show interest in studying educational material and possess characteristics such as independence, and secondly, by the conditions created by the teacher to intensify the educational process, as well as the chosen forms, active methods, and didactic tools.

When active teaching methods are appropriately and purposefully utilized, the ultimate outcome - educational effectiveness - will consistently surpass that of traditional education. Most importantly, it fosters the development of skills in students such as

independent thinking, finding autonomous solutions to various issues and problems, and self-monitoring. This, in turn, plays a crucial role as graduates of educational institutions take their first steps into independent life and find their place in the labor market.

The selection and application of active methods and techniques in higher education are reflected in the research works of L.V. Golish and B.S. Nuriddinov. Independent learning ensures that teachers achieve their educational goals and that students effectively assimilate educational materials within the framework of subject programs through independent work. Teachers, in turn, should encourage and properly guide students' aspirations for independent learning. Both the student and the teacher should know how to organize independent work better, more effectively, and more conveniently - whether the student works more efficiently alone; prefers working with a group of several people; spends time in the library; or finds it more convenient to use available electronic educational resources on the Internet. The main essence of independent learning is that students' source of knowledge should not be limited to the information provided by the teacher during classes. In the context of independent learning, students must understand and act upon the educational material they need to master, while teachers should encourage and guide students' research skills, prompting them to search for additional information to gain a deeper understanding of the covered material.

Independent learning should be carried out in accordance with the goals, principles, and content of education without external influence. Independent learning determines a student's autonomy in educational and professional activities. These qualities are manifested in understanding educational material and critically assessing current situations. An individual's independence is the unity of their unique characteristics, abilities, activity, thinking capacity, and dedication to achieving set goals. In independent learning, it is crucial to base the approach on didactic and pedagogical principles. Currently, through the effective organization of independent learning, students are encouraged to engage in creative activities and, consequently, pursue their own independent research. Independent learning places very important demands on pedagogical technology. Unlike the educational process in educational institutions where the final result of teacher-student collaborative activity is predetermined, in independent learning, the student must achieve an unpredictable and unplanned result. Specifically, they need to master a certain volume of knowledge, skills, and abilities related to the studied educational material. The goals, principles, methods, techniques, means, and conditions of independent learning must be clearly defined, and their appropriate selection and effective implementation will lead to the

desired result. Students should take responsibility for the quality of knowledge they acquire. The source of students' knowledge is not limited to the information presented in teachers' lectures; rather, students must understand and act on their own. Teachers, in turn, should encourage the development of students' research skills and their ability to find additional information for a deeper understanding of the studied material. Every future modern specialist must be prepared for independent learning and study in such a way that they not only understand current equipment and technology, but also can master new equipment and technology in a significantly shorter time and more effectively. It should be emphasized that fostering and developing creativity in future junior specialists is also a distinct pedagogical task, and the implementation of this task requires the development of specialized methodologies. The essence of the guiding text method is that students should learn independently as much as possible. Therefore, questions and tasks should be structured in such a way that they are primarily aimed at independent study.

Based on experiments conducted on applying the guiding text method to the teaching process, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Independent actions form the foundation of the learning and assimilation process;
- Activities during learning should be independently planned, implemented, verified, and evaluated by students;
- The work should encompass technical, occupational safety, legal, and environmental issues;
- Work activities should be integrated into students' knowledge and experience.

The questions and assignments given to students should have clearly defined learning objectives, meaning they should correspond to the specified learning content in terms of volume and complexity.

As a result of teaching students to work independently in specialized subjects in higher education, they develop abilities such as engaging in collaborative communication, planning, decision-making, and self-assessment of their work.

Summarizing the above, it can be said that it is both possible and necessary to develop students' skills in independent and creative work. Students' independent work activities can be fostered both during lessons and outside of class. Such development creates the necessary conditions for enhancing the student's level of consciousness, the quality of acquired knowledge, and the desire to learn, thus contributing to the upbringing of a worthy generation for the future of our country.

Conclusion: Through the maximum utilization of active teaching methods, it is possible to effectively achieve the educational goals set for specialized subjects,

activate students' learning activities, and attain learning outcomes. The essence and advantages of several active methods effectively used in higher education were elucidated. Any teacher of a specialized subject can ensure the effective achievement of learning objectives in their discipline through appropriate teaching methodology.

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